

Le Conflit d'Adam et Eve contre Satan ou The first and the Second hidden book of Adam and Eve صراع آدم وحواء ضد الشيطان

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Entry tags: Christian, Early Christianity, Egyptian Christianity, Religious Group, Coptic, Early Christianity, Early Christianity, Biblical Prophets, Arabian Religions, Text, Early Christianity in Egypt, Christian Theology, Christian Traditions, Early Christian Text

Ce livre est considéré comme l'un des livres les plus importants du christianisme oriental (copte et éthiopien), et il s'intéresse à ce dont les auteurs du Nouveau Testament ne se souciaient pas, à savoir le début de la création de l'homme et sa lutte contre Satan depuis Adam jusqu'à Noé. Ce livre est tiré des Apocryphes Chrétiens. Son contenu a été diffusé oralement du 4^{ème} siècle après JC au 8^{ème} siècle après JC. Ensuite, il a été écrit en arabe en Egypte au 9^{ème} ou 10^{ème} siècle après JC. Il a ensuite été traduit en langue abyssine. Au XIX^{ème} siècle, le père Migné le traduit en français, et le Révérend Malan en anglais, d'autres traductions ont été faites au cours du XX^{ème} siècle comme celle de Rutherford H. Platt Jr. en 1926, ou celle de la maison d'édition française Filbluz editions... sans oublier Lumpkin dans son "Encyclopedia of Lost and Rejected Scriptures; The Pseudepigrapha and Apocrypha". Ibrahim Salem al-Tarzi semble avoir traduit l'œuvre de Lumpkin, d'ailleurs c'est une traduction pleine de fautes et pauvre en références. Dans ce livre, on retrouve une présence intense de deux sources de "légende religieuse", à savoir : les sources chrétiennes orientales, en particulier le texte attribué à Ephraïm, qui est "La Caverne des Trésors", et les sources islamiques, en particulier les livres qui circulaient (sunnites et chiïtes) au IX^{ème} siècle en Egypte, au Sham et en Irak

Date Range: 300 CE - 990 CE

Region: Egypte Ethiopie

Region tags: Syria, Egypt, Ethiopie

Egypte

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: L'Abbé Migne, (éditeur), Dictionnaire des apocryphes ou collection de tous les livres apocryphes relatifs à l'ancien et au nouveau testament, (Paris 1856)
- Source 2: الطرزي، إبراهيم سالم، إبيحرافا وأبوكريفا العهد القديم لتجميع لكتابات الإبيحرافا وأبوكريفا القديم الكتاب الأول (أسفار جثة عدن المنسنة وأسفار قصة آدم وحواء، ط 1، 2006)
- Source 3: Charles, R. H., Pseudepigrapha of the Old Testament, (oxford, n.d.).
- Source 1: Quinn, Esther C., The Penitence of Adam a study of the Andrius ms., (Valencia, Spain, 1980)
- Source 2: Robinson, S.E., «The testament of Adam», in The Anchor Yale Bible Dictionary, V I,
- Source 3: Denis, Albert-Marie, Introduction aux Pseudepigraphes Grecs d'ancien Testament, (Brill, Leiden, 1970)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.sacred-texts.com/bib/fbe/fbe005.htm>
- Source 1 Description: Une copie électronique du livre sur le site Web sacred texts.com
- Source 2 URL: https://www.marefa.org/%D9%83%D9%86%D9%8A%D8%B3%D8%A9_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AA%D9%88%D8%AD%D9%8A%D8%AF_%D8%A
- Source 2 Description: Un article en arabe sur l'église éthiopienne

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.sacred-texts.com/bib/fbe/fbe005.htm>
- Source 1 Description: Une copie électronique du livre en anglais sur le site Web sacred texts.com
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/398/398-h/398-h.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Une copie électronique du livre en français sur le site gutenber.org

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

- Inked
 - with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

- Specify type of paper
 - Specify: Papier normal

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

- Tomb
 - No
- Cemetery
 - No
- Temple
 - Yes
- Shrine
 - No
- Altar
 - No
- Devotional marker
 - No
- Cenotaph
 - No
- Church
 - Yes
- Mosque
 - No
- Synagogue
 - No
- Triumphal Arch
 - No
- Monument

- No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - No
- ↳ Domestic contexts
 - No
- ↳ Library/archive
 - Yes
- ↳ Specify
 - Specify: Il est très probable qu'un Ms en arabe se trouve au Vatican

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Notes: C'est un texte chrétien qui se trouve dans les églises alors on peu dire qu'il y a des icones et des images dans le lieu ou il est stocké

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Notes: Le texte arabe "perdu" ou éthiopien trouvé sont dans une langue religieuse archaïque. Nos réponses se limitent aux traduction dans les langues anglaise, française et arabe "moderne"

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: ça dépend de la traduction, la traduction arabe n'est pas dans un langage archaïque quoiqu'elle est dans un langage strictement religieux. une édition anglaise du XIX siècle est écrite dans un anglais ancien. <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/398/398-h/398-h.htm>

Reference: Platt, Rutherford. "First Book of Adam and Eve". Accessed May 31, 2023. <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/398/398-h/398-h.htm>.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

- ↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?
 - No
- ↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?
 - No
- ↳ Possess its own distinct written language?
 - No
- ↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

 - Institutions
- ↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?
 - Yes

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
 This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.
 – Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?
 – Yes

- ↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?
 - Yes

Notes: Il faut signalé que le texte censé être le livre du premier et première être humains, le prosélytisme n'est pas clair mais on peut le voir dans les actes de l'esprit divin (le saint esprit) quand il fait ressusciter Adam et Eve. En revanche Le texte nous parle que ceux qui seront délivrés des maux et de la torture dans ce monde sont les croyants, Adam et les élus de ses fils feront donc du prosélytisme pour sauver l'humanité de la mort et des enfers. voir 1Adam and Eve 42: 8; 49: 9; 68: 23... voir plus précisément 2Adam and Eve: 8: 14-19. "14 "But now, O Seth, my son, place thyself at the head of thy people; tend them and watch over them in the fear of God; and lead them in the good way, Command them to fast unto God; and make them understand they ought not to hearken to Satan, lest he destroy them. 15 "Then, again, sever thy children and thy children's children from Cain's children; do not let them ever mix with those, nor come near them either in their words or in their deeds." 16 Then Adam let his blessing descend upon Seth, and upon his children, and upon all his children's children. 17 He then turned to his son Seth, and to Eve his wife, and said to them, "Preserve this gold, this incense, and this myrrh, that God has given us for a sign; for in days that are coming, a flood will overwhelm the whole creation. But those who shall go into the ark shall take with them the gold, the incense, and the myrrh, together with my body; and will lay the gold, the incense, and the myrrh, with my body in the midst of the earth. 18 "Then, after a long time, the city in which the gold, the incense, and the myrrh are found with my body, shall be plundered. But when it is spoiled, the gold the incense, and the myrrh shall be taken care of with the spoil that is kept; and naught of them shall perish, until the Word of God, made man shall come; when kings shall take them, and shall offer to Him, gold in token of His being King; incense, in token of His being God of heaven and earth; and myrrh, in token of His passion. 19 "Cold also, as a token of His overcoming Satan, and all our foes; incense as a token that He will rise from the dead, and be exalted above things in heaven and things in the earth; and myrrh, in token that He will drink bitter gall; and feel the pains of hell from Satan. 20 "And now, O Seth, my son, behold I have revealed unto thee hidden mysteries, which God had revealed unto me. Keep my commandment, for thyself, and for thy people," Platt, p 111.

Reference: Platt, Rutherford H. , ed.. The forgotten books of eden. Edited by Rutherford H. Platt. Vol. 1. New York: Alpha House, 1926.

- ↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Comme on peut le voir dans le rôle des fils d'Adam qui s'occupaient de leurs frères et sœurs
- ↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?
 - No
- ↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Même remarque on ne trouve pas des réponses claires sur ces questions, mais le texte appartient à la culture chrétienne qui nous offre la possibilité d'accepter, selon ce que se trouve dans le texte lui-même, la réponse affirmative
- ↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
 - No
 - Notes: L'expression dans un temps précis n'est claire, c'est pourquoi ma réponse est non car le prosélytisme chrétien en général, le texte n'est pas contre, n'est pas lié à un temps précis

- ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
 - No
 - Notes: Il s'adresse en théorie à tout le monde
- ↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
 - No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

- ↳ Is it orally recited?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is it read?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?
 - No
- ↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
 - Specify: Je ne sais pas
- ↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Parmi les indices que le livre a été écrit dans les derniers siècles du premier millénaire quelques chants et quelques rites qui n'existaient pas dans les premiers siècles du christianisme
- ↳ On average, how many participants are present?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
 - Yes
- ↳ On average, how many participants are present?
 - I don't know
- ↳ How often do the rituals take place?
 - Specify: Pas de précisions

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– Yes
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– Yes
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices?
– I don't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?
– No
- ↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?
– No

Is there material significance to the text?
– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?
– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?
– No

Notes: Il existerait un Ms arabe du texte au Vatican, il y a aussi une traduction éthiopienne et une multitude de traduction en français et en anglais. Il y a des textes qui sont très proche du notre comme "The Penitence of Adam", "Adam's Testament" ou The testament of Adam ou son traduction française "Le testament d'Adam", "Le Livre d'Adam" à consulter De Jonge, Marinus, and Tromp, Johannes p 16-17

Reference: De Jonge, Marinus, and Johannes Tromp. Life of Adam and Eve and Related Literature. UK: Sheffield Academic Press, 1997.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?
– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?
– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?
– Yes

Notes: Le texte appartient à la catégorie des livres apocryphes, C'est l'église éthiopienne en particulier et orthodoxe en général qui l'a qualifié en apocryphe

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?
– Yes

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?
– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?
– No

Notes: Il fait partie d'une série de livre mais non de volumes

Reference: Migné, Abbé. Dictionnaire Des Apocryphes Ou Collection De Tous Les Livres Apocryphes Relatifs À L'ancien Et Au Nouveau Testament. Paris.. Abbé Migné, 1856.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: Le texte fait partie des apocryphes, il est, néanmoins, lié à des livres oubliés (forgotten books), ou cachés (Hidden books)

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Manuel rituel; Vocabulaire

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: Commençant par Adam jusqu'à Noé

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Other [specify]: Elu spirituel; Liens de sang

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Notes: Ce n'est très clair mais nous sommes dans un contexte historique et social arabo-africain qui fait des mutations de la lune la base de son calendrier. Dans le chapitre de la mort d'Adam paragraphe 3 nous lisons dans la traduction anglaise: "The death of Adam took place at the end of nine hundred and thirty years that be lived upon the earth; on the fifteenth day of Barmudeh, after the reckoning of an epact of the sun, at the ninth hour" il n'y a pas une allusion à la lune. Dans la traduction de Tarzi en arabe: وقد حدث موت آدم عند من برمودة بعد حساب الفرق بين السنة الشمسية والسنة القمرية

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

Notes: On trouve des activités liées à la récolte mais elles ne sont pas liées à un temps précis

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– Yes

Notes: Non lié à un temps précis

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

- ↳ Marriage?
 - Yes
- ↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?
 - No
- ↳ Divorce?
 - No
- ↳ Warfare?
 - No
- ↳ Funerary services?
 - No
- ↳ Trade/commerce?
 - No
- ↳ Festivals?
 - No
- ↳ Pilgrimages?
 - No
- ↳ Feasting?
 - No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: La distinction entre esprit et corps est bien connu et acceptée chez les chrétiens, ce qui peut frapper aux yeux est que cette distinction peut s'exprimer parfois comme distinction entre homme (qui sera l'esprit) et la femme (qui sera le corps) voir Nicene and Post-Nicene Fathers, Ser. II, Vol. VI: Treatises: To Pammachius against John of Jerusalem, p 174. Voir référence p 26

Reference: De Jonge, Marinus, and Johannes Tromp. Life of Adam and Eve and Related Literature. UK: Sheffield Academic Press, 1997.

- ↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?
 - Yes
- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other spirit-body relationship?
 - Yes
 - Notes: C'est l'esprit qui est à la base de la vie du corps
- ↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?
 - Generally negative
 - ↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?
 - Specify: C'est le corps qui a subit le mal sensoriel après la chute, l'esprit en revanche a subit le mal de la solitude et de la peur su Satan

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: L'âme prime sur le corps.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Nous trouvons dans 1Adam and Eve: 45; 9-10 une brève description de la vie dans les enferts "9 God said also to Adam, "See this fire kindled by Satan around thy cave; see this wonder that surrounds thee; and know that it will encompass about both thee and thy seed, when ye hearken to his behest, that he will plague you with fire; and that ye shall go down into hell after ye are dead. 10 "Then shall ye see the burning of his fire, that will thus be burning around you and your seed. There shall be no deliverance from it for you, but at My coming; in like manner as thou canst not now go into thy cave, by reason of the great fire around it; not until My Word shall come that will make a way for thee on the day My covenant is fulfilled." voir The forgotten books of Eden p 51.

Reference: Platt, Rutherford H. , ed.. The forgotten books of eden. Edited by Rutherford H. Platt. Vol. 1. New York: Alpha House, 1926.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: Un débat sur le langage celeste, la langue de Dieu, nous oriente vers la question de la langue sacrée. Une langue c'est certainement la langue de Dieu suprême et ça doit être la langue de ses messages et livres envoyés à l'humanité. de ce point de vue l'hebrew, l'arabe, ou même le grecque ou autre langues peuvent être La langue divine. De plus le saint esprit peut donner la connaissance des langues aux saints qui n'ont jamais étudié ou connu ces langues. C'est pour cela, peut être, que Dieu dans le christianisme parle toute les langues. Michel Deneken disait à propos de l'approche herderienne dela problématique du langage divin: "Dans la première de ses lettres au sujet de l'enseignement de la théologie datée de 1784, Herder affirme que « la meilleure étude pour être enseigné des choses de Dieu est l'étude de la Bible et la meilleure des lectures possibles pour ce livre, c'est la manière humaine. Je prends ce mot dans le sens le plus large et le plus répandu. En quelque sorte, un accès est possible dans la Création au Créateur en raison du mystère du poème. » L'originalité de Herder dans cette réflexion se situe dans le refus de comprendre la langue de l'origine comme « sacrée » ; c'est une inversion qu'il propose en affirmant que la langue biblique est la langue de Dieu parce qu'elle est la plus humaine." voir Deneken, Michel p 496

Reference: Deneken, Michel. "Quand dieu apprend à parler aux hommes : herder et la bible". Accessed June 2, 2023. <https://www.cairn.info/revue-recherches-de-science-religieuse-2002-4-page-487.htm>.

Reference: Deneken, Michel. "Quand dieu apprend à parler aux hommes : herder et la bible". *Recherches de science religieuse* 90 (April 2002): 487-508.

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?
– Specify: L'interprétation ésotérique

↳ What are the historically minority positions?
– Specify: La position exotérique

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?
– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?
– Yes

↳ Cremation?
– No

↳ Mummification?
– No

↳ Interment?
– Yes

↳ Cannibalism?
– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?
– No

↳ Feeding to animals?
– No

↳ Secondary burial?
– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?
– Yes
Notes: On lit ce traitement à propos du cadavre d'Adam. voir 2Adam and Eve: 9: 4-5

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?
– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?
– No

↳ Other instensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?
– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?
– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present?
– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present?

– Yes

↳ Of what type, if known?
– Specify: très probablement des agneaux

↳ How many?
– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?
– No

↳ In cemetery?
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?
– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?
– Yes

Notes: Seulement pour Adam, le texte n'indique pas un lieu domestique peut être parceque la distinction entre lieu domestique et lieu de travail ou autre n'est pas très claire

↳ Other formal burial type?
– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual
– Specify: 2Adam and Eve 9: 4: "Then Seth wound him up well, and embalmed him with plenty of sweet spices, from sacred trees and from the Holy Mountain; and be laid his body on the eastern side of the inside of the cave, the side of the incense; and placed in front of him a lamp-stand kept burning."

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Adam et Eve sont confrontés au Diable et ses soldats, aidés par le Mot de Dieu

↳ A supreme high-god is present
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms
– Yes
Notes: Il est décrit en terme anthropomorphes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god
– Specify: Omniprésent, Puissant, ...

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes

Notes: Rien ne lui échappe

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Notes: Malgré que les chrétienne croient que Jésus est Dieu et qu'il a été blessé, frappé et humilié, nous ne trouvons pas dans ce texte des indications clair que Dieu peut être blessé

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Notes: C'est un peu compliquer, le texte parle du mot de Dieu qui redonne vie à Adam et Eve et que Dieu rappelle son mot après avoir accompli sa tâche. les chrétiens censé adorer ce mot qui sera le Christ

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: Il est le plus puissant

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: Toute communication n'est pas directe sauf avec Adam quand il était dans le jardin d'Eden

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Notes: Mais ce sont eux qui peuvent interpréter le message divin

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Des visions

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Notes: Le livre nous parle des premiers figures bibliques qui vivaient sur une montagne sacrée ce qui leur donnait la possibilité de communiquer avec Dieu

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– I don't know

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Notes: clairvoyance, perspicacité, vision du monde divin, conscience de l'agence divine omniprésente ou omnipotence, soupir ou vision au-delà des cinq sens.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: Adam est le premier être humain (corps et esprit)

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Satan, les anges et l'esprit divin

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: D'Adam à Noé ces figures bibliques peuvent voir ces êtres surnaturels

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: D'Adam à Noé ces figures bibliques peuvent ressentir physiquement ces êtres surnaturels

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Il faut distinguer entre les anges et les esprits malifiques d'un côté et l'esprit de Dieu de l'autre, en ce qui concerne l'esprit de Dieu les réponses présentées aux questions du Dieu suprême sont valables aussi pour l'esprit de Dieu

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

- No
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists?
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch?
 - No
 - ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Non
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - No
 - Notes: Sauf pour les esprits du mal
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: Ils sont plus fort que l'Homme

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
– No

- ↳ Organized hierarchically?
– Yes

- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
– No

- ↳ Other organization of pantheon?
– Specify: En groupe:: groupe des esprits du mal et groupe des esprits du bien

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?
– No

- ↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?
– Yes

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Les animaux

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

- ↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

- ↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– Yes

- ↳ Food
– Yes

- ↳ Sacred space(s)
– Yes

- ↳ Sacred object(s)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - Yes
- ↳ Adultery
 - Yes
- ↳ Incest
 - Yes
- ↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].
 - No
- ↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
 - No
- ↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
 - No
- ↳ Other sexual practices
 - No

Notes: Il est indiqué qu'Adam n'avait que 3 fils Abel, Qayin et Seth. Alors que chez les musulmans Adam ne mourru qu'après avoir vu des millier de ses fils et petit fils. Je crois que l'idée que les rapports sexuels même s'ils sont légitimes sont mal vu chez les chrétiens alors que les musulmans les considèrent comme indices de force et de virilité.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
 - Notes: 2Adam and Eve: 10: 3 "And when they had ended their offering, the Word of God came to Seth, the eldest among them, saying unto him, "O Seth, Seth, Seth, three times. As I was with thy father, so also shall I be with thee, until the fulfilment of the promise I made him-thy father saying, I will send My Word and save thee and thy seed."
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: Rien à préciser

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: Le texte n'indique clairement que le moment de la fin du monde ou du commencement de la fin du monde. On ne trouve pas le monde eschatologique (imaginaire et symbolique) de la Révélation, tout ce dont il parle est que Dieu (ou la parole de Dieu) descendra dans la fin des temps pour délivrer Adam et Eve des conséquences du péché. 1Adam and Eve: 22:6 "Then God said again unto Adam, "Because thou hast borne fear and trembling in this land, languor and suffering treading and walking about, going upon this mountain, and dying from it, I will take all this upon Myself in order to save thee."

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Strongly present & highlighted

Notes: Le livre est destiné à faire voir et valoir le combat entre Adam et Eve (l'Homme) contre Satan, c'est le bien contre le mal, le péché contre le repentir

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts
– Yes

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities
– Yes

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)
– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– No

↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity
– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: Les filles des hommes ont séduit les fils de Dieu

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: Réduire les rapports sexuels entre le mari et sa femme au minimum

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: Réduire les rapports sexuels entre la femme et son mari au minimum

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: En contre partie il est dit qu'Adam et Eve sont restés presque 40 jours dans l'eau invoquant Dieu pour qu'il pardonne leur péché

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Notes: La question est ambiguë quand nous pensons aux relations établi par le texte entre les fils de Seth et les fils de Cain, Seth demande toujours à ses fils de rester à l'écart des fils de Cain

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Il est compris du texte qu'Adam présente des sacrifices rituels chaque semaine, à l'époque de ses fils l'intervalle n'est pas claire

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– No

↳ Food taboos?

– Yes

↳ Hair?

– No

↳ Dress?

– No

↳ Ornaments?

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Les fils du Dieu (les gentils)

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: La réponse est non sauf si on considère, la narration, une activité divertissante

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: Il y a ici une remarque importante à propos du sacrifice. Les offrandes présentées par le couple humain sont des sacrifices des animaux, mais ici le texte nous parle de sacrifice humain et divin 1Adam et Eve: 24: 1-6. "TEN the merciful God, good 'and lover of men, looked upon Adam and Eve, and upon their blood, which they had held up as an offering unto Him; without an order from Him for so doing. But He wondered at them; and accepted their offerings. 2 And God sent from His presence a bright fire, that consumed their offering. 3 He smelt the sweet savour of their offering, and showed them mercy. 4 Then came the Word of God to Adam, and said unto him, "O Adam, as thou hast shed thy blood, so will I shed My own blood when I become flesh of thy seed; and as thou didst die, O Adam, so also will I die. And as thou didst build an altar, so also will I make for thee an altar on the earth; and as thou didst offer thy blood upon it, so also will I offer My blood upon an altar on the earth. 5 "And as thou didst sue for forgiveness through that blood, so also will I make My blood forgiveness of sins, and blot out transgressions in it. 6 "And now, behold, I have accepted thy offering, O Adam, but the days of the covenant, wherein I have bound thee, are not fulfilled. When they are fulfilled, then will I bring thee back into the garden.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Oui mais appliqué seulement à Adam 1Adam et Eve 24: 1-6

↳ Suicide?

– No

↳ Bloodletting?

– Yes

↳ Mutilation?

– No

↳ Is self-sacrifice common and/or expected of elites?

– No

Notes: Non sauf si nous considérons que tout éloignement des plaisirs est une abnégation

↳ Are there material offerings present?

- Yes
 - ↳ Are they mandatory?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
 - No
 - ↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
 - No
 - ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Dans la tombe d'Adam
 - ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - No
 - ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (i.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - No
 - ↳ Other?
 - Specify: RS
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - Yes
 - ↳ By the community?
 - Yes
 - ↳ By specific individuals?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Une Eglise, il est probable que ce soit l'église orthodoxe égyptienne

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Le texte a été découvert vers le commencement du XIX siècle. Il est resté caché (Hidden book) dans l'église éthiopienne ou même copte

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Selon les textes chrétiens l'homme (le male) a des privilèges comparé à la femme

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Les enseignants dans le texte sont les "prophètes" comme Adam Seth et Noé

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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